

Status of E-Banking in India: Benefits and Issues

Dr. Santosh Solanki

Dr. Shiv Shankar Vishwakarma

Associate Professor-LNCT-MBA

Abstract

E-Banking has become an important factor in the future development of banking industry. Electronic banking or online banking is a service provide by many banks that allow handling of all types of banking business, primarily over the internet by using the information technology and communication. In many developed countries E- banking plays a very vital role due to the fact that it's the cheapest way of providing banking services. Beside this it also facilitated swift movement of funds domestically and across borders. E-Banking is one of the most successful on-line businesses, which save the time and money of customers and companies. It is easily accessible anywhere to a PC, PDA, mobile device, with an internet connection. It also enables the customer to conduct financial transactions on the website of the institution, such as virtual bank, retail bank, a credit union etc. Despite of many benefits of E-Banking, there are some factors which affect its usage. This research paper will introduce you to e-banking, giving the meaning, functions, types, advantages and issues. In short e-banking is anytime and anywhere banking

1. Defining Electronic banking

Electronic banking is a form of banking in which funds are transferred through an exchange of electronic signals rather than through an exchange of cash, checks, or other types of paper documents. Transactions like account transfers, balance enquiries, bill payments, etc. are done through this system. Some banks offer services like loan, credit card applications form through this system. The banking activities can be classified as transactional and non- transactional activities. Electronic transfer of funds, Payment of bills, Loan & credit card application Investment products are few of transactional activities and Viewing of account balance, Viewing of previous transactions, Downloading of Bank statement, Ordering Check book, mobile banking and internet banking application forms are few of non-transactional activities.

2. Current Scenario of E- Banking in India

Electronic banking is inferred to be safe and secured, compared to physical banking. It ensures qualitative banking operations compared to traditional banking. E-banking in India is still in the early stages of growth and development. Competition and changes in technology have changed the face of the banking sector.

It provides universal connection from any location worldwide and is universally accessible from any internet linked computer. Information technology developments in the banking sector have speed up communication and transactions for clients. It is vital to extend this banking feature to clients for maximizing the advantages for both clients and service providers.

Received: 24 May 2023

Revised: 12 June 2023

Final Accepted: 25 June 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

Internet is the cheapest delivery channel for banking products as it allows the entity to reduce their branch networks and downsize the number of service staff. The navigability of the Website is a very important part of internet banking because it can become one of the biggest competitive advantages of a financial entity. Bankers consider 'minimizes inconvenience', 'minimizes cost of transactions' and 'time saving' to be important benefits and 'chances of government access', 'chances of fraud' and 'lack of Information security' to be vital risks associated with electronic banking. Due to increase in technology usage the banking sector's performance increases day by day. Internet banking is becoming the indispensable part of modern day banking service.

After the **COVID-19** pandemic outbreak, the demand for online banking platforms in India experienced phenomenal development. Customers and businesses quickly migrated to digital banking platforms, as a result, greatly accelerating market growth.

3. Research Significance

The banking industry, being backbone of Indian economy is undergoing vast changes. Advancement in information technology, global business development and demand from customers has paved way for changes in the banking scenario. The study is a bird's eye view of E-banking in India. After demonetization, remonetization has taken place. Due to the advancement of technology, banking sector looks ahead for more paperless transactions. This was considered as right time to study about the usage of electronic banking system in India. The study aims to understand the awareness about the electronic banking system in India.

4. E-Banking Services

Services covered under E-banking as follows

- i. **Internet Banking :-** Web-based banking is an assistance presented by banks that permits account holders to get their record information by means of the web or the internet. Web-based banking or Internet banking is otherwise called "Web banking" or "Online banking."
- ii. **UPI (Unified Payment Interface):-** Unified Payments Interface (UPI) is a payment system that allows users to link more than one bank account in a single smartphone app and make fund transfers without having to provide IFSC code or account number.
- iii. **Mobile Banking:-** Mobile banking refers to the use of a mobile device, such as a smartphone or tablet, to access and manage one's banking accounts and conduct various financial transactions. Mobile banking apps offer a convenient and secure way to manage one's finances on the go, without the need to visit a bank branch or ATM.
- iv. **Banking Cards:-** Debit cards let you buy things without carrying cash. You can use your debit card in most stores to pay for something. You just swipe the card and enter your PIN number on a key pad. Debit cards take money out of your checking account immediately.
- v. **Mobile Wallets:-** There are three types of mobile wallets in India – open, semi-closed and closed.

- **Open wallets** – can only be issued by the banks. They allow you to purchase goods and services, cash withdrawal at ATMs and to transfer funds.
 - **Semi-closed wallets** – have a specific contract with the issuer to accept the payment instruments. They will allow you to buy goods and services or perform financial services at clearly identified merchant locations.
 - **Closed wallets** – are accounts issued by a company to a consumer for buying goods and services exclusively from that company. Here a certain amount of money is locked with the company in case of a cancellation or return of the order, or gift cards.
- vi. **Bharat Interface For Money:-** Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM) is a mobile payments application based on NPCI's Unified Payments Interface (UPI). BHIM is developed by the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI)—the umbrella organization for all retail payment systems in India.
- vii. **Point of Sale (PoS):-** Point of sale (POS) refers to the payment counter in a retail store where customers pay for their purchased goods. When a customer picks out a product and wants to check them out, a culmination of hardware and software helps businesses make those sales. It helps customer management be easier and the time taken is the bare minimum.

All Banks are making greater use of E-banking facilities to provide best service and to face cut throat competition at entire globe. The spread of E-banking is also greatly helping the ordinary rural customers.

5. Benefits of E-Banking:

E banking ensures various attractive services for banks and customer's. e-banking has made life much easier and banking much faster for both customers and banks.

- It saves time spent in banks
- It provides ways for international banking.
- It provides banking throughout the year 24/7 days from any place have internet access.
- It provides well-organized cash management for internet optimization
- It provides convenience in terms of capital, labour, time all the resources needed to make a transaction.
- Taking advantage of integrated banking services, banks may compete in new markets, can get new customers and grow their market share.
- It provides some security and privacy to customers, by using state-of-the-art encryption and security technologies.

6. What are the risks of e-banking?

Despite many security measures in place, some risks are still associated with using e-banking services. These include:

- **Traditional banking habits:** Most of the US adults participate in online banking, on the other hand, there are still some people who don't use online banking. A majority of such people are well versed in traditional banking. Such resistance to change is typically due to a lack of trust in the online system or the incompetence to operate online portals.
- **Security and fraud instances:** This is one of the most significant challenges for banks promoting online banking. In traditional banking, robbers break into the banks to steal money, whereas in online banking hackers can break into customers details and illegally transfer money. For example, in 2015, around 130 million British pounds were stolen from online bank accounts through fraud. The extension of e-commerce provides a chance for fraudsters to misuse payment networks and steal sensitive information.
- **Training the Employees:** Training imparted to bank employees is an easier task in case of private sector banks, as they have young dynamic computer literate employees, while in case of public sector banks, training the employees is a complex task as present staff is comparatively lesser computer literate. In spite of this fact, they have been able to do influentially well after functioning on it for over a decade now.
- **Identity Theft:** If your personal information is stolen, it could be used to access your account and conduct fraudulent transactions
- **Phishing Scams:-** Criminals may trick you into disclosing your login details or other sensitive information by impersonating a bank or other trusted organisation
- **Malware:-** Malicious software (malware) can be used to infect your computer and gain access to your account. In case you click a malicious link or download an infected file, this can happen.
- **Legal Risk:-** Whenever there is a violation of laws, regulations, or prescribed practices, or when the legal rights and obligations of any of the parties to a transaction are not established, then there is a legal risk involved. E-Banking is relatively new to the industry and there is a lot of uncertainty and ambiguity about certain laws and rules. This increases the legal risk.

7. The Future E-Banking:-

The financial sector has witnessed significant evolution and continues to expand. It has seen the most significant advancements moving towards digitization.

Here are the top transformations offered by technology in the banking sector.

1- Improving Customer Experience:- Online banking provides customers a faster and smoother banking experience without waiting in long queues.

It includes services like online transactions, money transfers, and chatbot assistance services which helps customers save time. It can help resolve their issues from home, and make transactions in seconds, which enhances their overall experience.

2- Customizing Services:- With the growing technology, banks use artificial intelligence and data analytics to offer customers customized services.

By collecting customer data, banks can gain insights into the customer's preferences and need to develop strategies and provide services accordingly. It also helps to gain customer loyalty while providing a personalized experience.

3- Boosting Blockchain Technology:- With the help of blockchain technology, banks can offer more secure ways to store customer data for making transactions.

It can offer transparency to the customers for the banking processes and create a secure customer identity for digital verification. It can prevent fraud and streamline finance processes by creating a safe environment for sharing information with the parties involved.

4- Revolutionizing Banking Sector Using IoT:- IoT, or the Internet of Things, is a great way to revolutionize the banking industry by delivering innovative services and enhancing payment processor efficiency while strengthening customer support.

It can help optimize operations and increase cyber security with the help of sensors to collect data from ATMs, contactless payments, or mobile banking applications. It can alert the responsible maintenance team if an issue prevents downtime and ensures a smoother experience.

5- Transforming New Age Software Development:-With the increase in innovations in the banking sector, new-age business models are also developed.

Banks are partnering with fintech companies that offer banking software development. Such software provides data and customer management services, core and on-demand functionality, security, and all basic banking operations. It also helps banking services reach people nationwide while allowing access to a greater area.

8. Conclusion

India is going through an environment of change in banking and financial technology, led by an amazing talent base. With a mindset to adapt, a simultaneous effort from the government and the watchful eye of RBI, innovation in digital banking will charter new areas of customer inclusion. With the introduction of the Digital Banking Unit (DBU), a minimum digital infrastructure hub delivering banking services and the future inclusion of metaverse in digital banking with its huge potential, the future of digital banking looks promising and optimistic.

REFERENCES:

- <https://www.financemagnates.com/fintech/education-centre/2023-digital-banking-trends-and-the-future-of-banking/>
- <https://ecommercefastlane.com/the-future-of-e-banking-how-technology-is-changing-ecommerce-banking/>
- <https://www.enterpriseitworld.com/future-of-digital-banking/>
- <https://www.ijert.org/electronic-banking-in-india-innovations-challenges-and-opportunities>
- N. Jamaluddin (2013). E-Banking-Challenges and Opportunities in India. International Business conference, Australia, 1-15.
- Tarandeep Kaur (2015). Transformation from e-commerce to m-commerce In India. Sai Om Journal of Commerce & Management. 2(12), 9-17.
- <https://www.wallstreetmojo.com/point-of-sale/>
- Singh P. (2013). “An exploratory study on internet banking uses in semi urban areas in India”, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Vol. 3, No. 8: pp. 1-5